

The Coupling Constants Series and Spin Representation – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series and in particular using the prime critical line we can reach wonderful representation of spin, and describe the process of propagation of bosons from fermion clusters.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right]$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right]$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right]$$

Since (3) is a prime, and aligned on the prime ring located on critical line of $\frac{1}{2}$. The sums alongside of it are even sums such as 8, 24, 120 and so on. These expressions are interesting, as one believes they represent the notion of matter or fermions. Notice that we omitted the additional net variation, which is also prime. Meaning it is also on the Prime Ring Located on $\frac{1}{2}$. Overall:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

So the construction within the parenthesis is prime but the overall additional net is changing it, and making it: $(1/2 + 1/2) = 1$. So the overall 1: 30: 128 will have to do with certain elements that have element one. We already knows these are bosons, as we found the coupling constants series. If so, than the rest of the terms are fermions, as only $(1/2)$ is there.

So it is the Majestic (3) →in this paper: $(1/2)$ element to destabilize Perfect clusters of variations and causing a net variation to appear. Notice that one chose the first option in regards to the meaning of the invariant (3), as we had in part two three ideas to it possible meaning. We have proved that the Majestic (3) is Spin. We also proved, that bosons will propagate within variation clusters destabilized by $(1/2)$, or matter. These are non-trivial statements. We only use one equation, not experiment nor inherited knowledge. **Using that framework, we can see why bosons will propagate within fermions.** Since Its invariant, all matter must have the same spin, $1/2$.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)